

Genus *Crotalaria* XII¹. Identity of Crotalaburnine as Anacrotine

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The pyrrolizidine macrocyclic diester alkaloid anacrotine², C₁₈H₂₅NO₆, m.p. 191-192° (Mattocks³, m.p. 195°), [α]_D²⁰+30° (ethanol), picrate m.p. 224° (d), methiodide m.p. 222° has been reported to occur in *Crotalaria anagyroides*², *C. laburnifolia*^{4 5} and *C. incana*³. Emmanuel and Ghosh⁶ reported the isolation of an uncharacterised alkaloid C₁₆H₂₃NO₅, m.p. 184-186° (d) from seeds of *C. laburnifolia*. Later on Snehlata *et al*⁷ confirmed the occurrence of this erroneously formulated (C₁₆H₂₃NO₅) alkaloid and simply gave it a new name crotalaburnine without commenting on its structure. Seshadri and Co-workers⁸ also recorded the isolation of crotalaburnine, C₁₈H₂₅NO₆, m.p. 197-199° (d), [α]_D²⁵+29.7° (ethanol), picrate m.p. 222-224° (d) and methiodide m.p. 220-222° (d). The alkaloid was obviously anacrotine but unfortunately the authors insisted in retaining the name crotalaburnine.

At present, there is a confusion in literature regarding the correlation between anacrotine and crotalaburnine. We have now directly compared crotalaburnine with anacrotine, isolated by us from *C. laburnifolia* seeds. The two alkaloids have identical m.p. and mixed m.p., same *R_f* values on t.l.c (silicagel G, solvent systems (a) methanol, (b) chloroform-methanol-ammonia 85 : 14 : 1) and paper chromatography (solvent system: upper layer resulted from shaking equal volumes of *n*-butanol with 5% acetic acid). The NMR (Fig. 1) for assignments see ref. 2) and IR (Fig. 2) spectra are also superimposable ; thus confirming that the two alkaloids are identical.

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